

ISic2725

I.Sicily inscription 2725

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Euonymus

Place of origin (modern)

Panarea

Provenance

Found in localita San Pietro (east coast of island), in 1975 (work near
Hotel Raya)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Panarea, private collection

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334833

1. Ναίιος
2. Πομπήϊος
3. Κλᾶρος.
- 4.

Apparatus**Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 645145

EDCS 71000721

PHI 334833

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1388

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 725

Giustolisi, V. 1995. Vulcano. Introduzione alla storia e all'archeologia dell'antica Hiera. Palermo. At 15

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2725. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387309>